

METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE

Andijan Region Institute of Foreign Languages

3rd level student of the Faculty of English Philology, Teaching Methodology and Translation Studies, Foreign Language and Literature (English)

Shodmonaliyeva Muhliisa Ilhomjon qizi

***Abstract:** In this article highlights of using innovative methods in the teaching English language.*

***Key words:** multimedia programs, project method, brainstorming, Internet.*

At the present stage of development of science, technology, international trade, various types of business communication, knowledge of foreign languages is not only a necessity, but also a need for specialists. There are many traditional methods of teaching foreign languages, which are quite effective. However, the modern development of society requires the search and use of more advanced methods and technologies. Knowledge of several languages becomes the norm. For fast and effective learning of foreign languages, innovative techniques are needed, aimed at developing practical skills of a qualified specialist who is able to solve professional tasks at the level of foreign language communicative competence. When teaching students foreign languages, the most effective methods are the following: multimedia presentation, project method, testing interactive programs on-line (for example, TOEFL), on-line modules, interactive boards, multimedia programs, creating a student's language portfolio, case method (based on the situational method of training), competence analysis (represents the assessment of game participants by competence, the construction of specialty programmiograms), distance learning, etc. Innovative methods allow achieving whose goals are: 1)

systematization of knowledge; 2) development of trainees' creative abilities; 3) self-education; 4) understanding of the educational material, analysis of the learned material. One of the modern methods of teaching foreign languages is the use of computer technology. Computer language programs bring diversity to the learning process, contribute to creating a favorable creative atmosphere and, at the same time, individualize the learning process and make it easier to exercise ongoing control. Multimedia programs increase learning efficiency, interest in learning foreign languages, expand the possibilities of perception and assimilation of educational material (using video, graphics, testing, etc.), and also allow you to distribute tasks in a group by degree of difficulty. An important point in learning a foreign language is the stage of reflection. Using a computer, students have the opportunity to analyze the results of their activities. Of particular interest to students are the multimedia programs "Learn to speak English", the London language course "BBC" (intermediate and advanced levels), the electronic encyclopedia "Encarta", "The British Encyclopedia". Multimedia programs have a number of advantages, which are expressed in the following: 1) the use of fascinating regional geographic videos with text support, which can be eliminated when specifying increased complexity; 2) virtual voice contact with native speakers, the opportunity for the learner to become a participant in the events, to control the quality of foreign language communication; 3) the opportunity for the learner to make an audio recording of his own speech and compare the correctness of pronunciation on an evaluation scale; 4) the possibility of fixing grammatical material using games. Thus, multimedia programs motivate students to learn a foreign language, provide an opportunity to effectively work out and independently monitor phonetic, lexical and grammatical skills. Computer programs develop students' cognitive activity, their intellectual abilities, logical thinking, memory,

attention, and imagination. The project method is one of the most effective ways of organizing students' independent work, which is used at the final stage of studying a topic, that is, as a consolidation or in the process of repetition. The project method allows you to individualize the learning process, provides an opportunity for students to independently plan, implement and monitor their activities. Using the design methodology, students can independently choose sources of information, forms of presentation of the material and show their creative abilities to the full. Project work includes several stages. At the first stage, the content and nature of the project, sources and methods of finding information are discussed, individual tasks or tasks for microgroups are distributed. Groups are formed according to the level of language proficiency, psychological characteristics, and creative abilities. At the second stage, work is carried out directly with the projects, namely: collecting, summarizing and analyzing information; information exchange; compiling an active dictionary; writing a personal project; creation of slides, drawings, posters, etc. The third stage is the presentation of the project. During the presentation, students demonstrate fluency in a foreign language, demonstrate both prepared and spontaneous speech, especially after the presentation when discussing a project. Work on the project, of course, increases interest in learning foreign languages. Motivation helps students activate their cognitive and communication skills. The brainstorming method allows us to consider a variety of ideas: all participants discuss and prove their working hypothesis, reinforcing it with arguments. In the end, "brainstorming" is a collective decision of a problem, taken from a real situation or invented. Thus, the use of "brainstorming" allows students to gain useful managerial and organizational experience. Thus, the use of a variety of innovative methods of teaching foreign languages has a number of advantages that help teach students to

actively acquire new knowledge, develop their creative and organizational skills, and give a powerful incentive to learn the language. Innovative technologies make it ideal to combine theory with practice, form knowledge on the subject, professional skills and abilities.

References:

1. Boltaeva M. L. A business game in training [Text] / M. L. Boltaeva // Young Scientist. - 2012. - № 2. - p. 252–254.
2. Tatarinova M. A. Pedagogical technologies of teaching foreign languages using web technologies // <http://www.slideshare.net/Vladimirova/ss-1899757>.
3. Hakimov, S., & Dadaxanov, F. (2022). STATE OF HEAT CONDUCTIVITY OF WALLS OF RESIDENTIAL BUILDINGS. *Science and innovation*, 1(C7), 223-226.
4. Yuldashev, S., & Hakimov, S. (2022). ТЕМИР ЙЎЛ ТРАНСПОРТИДАН КЕЛИБ ЧИҚАДИГАН ТЕБРАНИШЛАР ҲАҚИДА. *Science and innovation*, 1(A5), 376-379
5. Yuvmitov, A., & Hakimov, S. R. (2021). Influence of seismic isolation on the stress-strain state of buildings. *Acta of Turin Polytechnic University in Tashkent*, 11(1), 71-79.
6. Шаропов, Б. Х., Хакимов, С. Р., & Рахимова, С. (2021). Оптимизация режимов гелиотеплохимической обработки золоцементных композиций. *Матрица научного познания*, (12-1), 115-123.
7. Ювмитов, А. С., & Хакимов, С. Р. (2020). ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ ВЛИЯНИЯ СЕЙСМОИЗОЛЯЦИИ НА ДИНАМИЧЕСКИЕ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКИ ЗДАНИЯ. *Acta of Turin Polytechnic University in Tashkent*, 10(2), 14.
8. Хакимов, С. (2022). АКТИВ ВА ПАССИВ СЕЙСМИК УСУЛЛАРИ ҲАМДА УЛАРНИНГ АСОСИЙ ВАЗИФАЛАРИ. *Journal of Integrated Education and Research*, 1(2), 30-36.
9. Хакимов, С., Шаропов, Б., & Абдуназаров, А. (2022). БИНО ВА ИНШОТЛАРНИНГ СЕЙСМИК МУСТАҲКАМЛИГИ БЎЙИЧА ХОРИЖИЙ ДАВЛАТЛАР (РОССИЯ, ЯПОНИЯ, ХИТОЙ, АҚШ) МЕЪЁРИЙ ХУЖЖАТЛАРИ ТАҲЛИЛИ. *BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 806-809.